

EXACT ELASTICITY SOLUTION FOR BUCKLING OF COMPOSITES

Aditi Chattopadhyay and Haozhong Gu
Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ 85287-6106, USA

ABSTRACT

An exact elasticity solution is presented for the buckling of a simply-supported orthotropic plate whose behavior is referred to as cylindrical bending. The general class of problems involving the geometric configuration of any number of orthotropic layers bonded together and subjected to an inplane compressive load is also analyzed by making use of the uniform prebuckling stress assumption which is equivalent to the membrane assumption used in plate theories. The closed-form expressions for the displacements and stresses are derived and the nonlinear eigenvalue equations are presented which are used to solve for critical loads. The results obtained from the exact solution are compared with the critical loads furnished by the classical laminate theory, the first order-and the refined third-order shear deformation theory. The solution provides a means of accurate assessment of existing two-dimensional plate theories.

INTRODUCTION

Anisotropic plates and laminated composite plates are usually analyzed by using approximate two-dimensional theories^[1-3] based on either the classical Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis of nondeformable normals and transverse shears, or the refined displacement field accounting for the effects of transverse shear deformation and normal stress. Among the characteristics of these two-dimensional theories, which limit its generality in the description of laminate response, are the approximation of inplane displacements through the thickness, particularly for laminates in which the stiffness properties vary dramatically from layer to layer. Other important limiting factors are the presence of boundary conditions in the plate theories which precludes the precise calculation of boundary layer effects, such as stress concentration factors and the approximation of shear deformation, implied by the hypothesis of plate theories. Finally the assumption of a state of plane stress in the constitutive relations eliminates the possibility of rigorous calculation of interlaminar stresses.

To assess the validity of these approximate theories, rigorous analytical solutions based on the exact theory of elasticity should be obtained for plate problems which is amenable to such analysis. Such benchmark elasticity solutions are valuable for laminated composite plates with inherent anisotropy in material and inherent inhomogeneity among the different layers. The anisotropy and inhomogeneity lead to considerable warping of the normal to the middle surface of the plate and cause abrupt variations of stresses at the interfaces of the laminate. A number of elasticity solutions are available for composite plates subjected to a transverse load distribution. Pagano^[4] first analyzed the cylindrical bending of a simply-supported composite laminates under sinusoidal transverse loads. Later investigations include bending of finite rectangular plates^[5,6], off-axial layers^[7,8], and localized loading^[9]. These elasticity solutions have enabled us to quantify the errors associated with various laminated plate theories^[10].

To address the problem of buckling of composite plates subjected to axial compression, early researches have been conducted though the application of classical laminate theory^[11]. For more accurate representations of the transverse shear and the transverse normal effects, various modifications in the classical theory of laminated plate have been performed^[1-3, 12, 13]. These higher-order plate theories can be applied to the buckling problems with the potential of improved

predictions of the critical load. However, no effort has been reported in presenting a solution based on the theory of elasticity to the problem of buckling of composite plate, against which results from various plate theories could be compared.

Towards this objective, an exact elasticity solution is presented for buckling of simply-supported orthotropic plates and laminated composite plates whose behaviors are referred to as cylindrical bending. Numerical results are presented for a single-layer orthotropic plate, a three-layer cross-ply laminated plate and a four-layer angle-ply laminated plate under axial compressive pressure and are compared with those obtained using several different plate theories. The developed theory therefore serves as a tool to assess the accuracy of the classical plate theory and existing improved plate theories for composites with moderately thick and thick constructions.

SOLUTION FOR ORTHOTROPIC PLATES

Fig.1 Geometry of the composite plate

For an elastic body in a state of plane strain with respect to the xz plane (Fig.1), the equations of equilibrium are written in terms of the two-dimensional stress tensor Σ and the two-dimensional deformation gradient \mathbf{F} as follows.

$$\text{div} (\Sigma \bullet \mathbf{F}^T) = 0 \tag{1}$$

where the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} can be expressed by the derivatives of the displacements u and w .

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + u_{,x} & u_{,z} \\ w_{,x} & 1 + w_{,z} \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

where the comma denotes partial differentiation with respect to the index that follows. At the critical load, there are two possible infinitely close positions of equilibrium. Using the superscript $()^0$ to denote the components of the stresses or the displacements corresponding to the primary position, a perturbed position is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= \sigma_x^0 + \alpha \sigma_x^1, & \sigma_z &= \sigma_z^0 + \alpha \sigma_z^1, & \tau_{xz} &= \tau_{xz}^0 + \alpha \tau_{xz}^1 \\ u &= u^0 + \alpha u^1, & w &= w^0 + \alpha w^1 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where σ_x is the inplane stress along x -direction, σ_z is the transverse normal stress, τ_{xz} is the transverse shear stress, α is an infinitesimally small quantity and $\alpha ()^1$ are the stresses or the displacements to which the points of the body must be subject in order to shift them from the initial position of equilibrium to the new equilibrium position. Inserting Eq.(3) into Eq.(1) and collecting the α terms, the buckling equations are obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} &[\sigma_x(1 + u_{,x}^0) + \tau_{xz}u_{,z}^0 + \sigma_x^0(1 + u_{,x}) + \tau_{xz}^0u_{,z}]_{,x} + [\tau_{xz}(1 + u_{,x}^0) + \sigma_zu_{,z}^0 \\ &+ \tau_{xz}^0(1 + u_{,x}) + \sigma_z^0u_{,z}]_{,z} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$[\sigma_x w_{,x}^0 + \tau_{xz}(1 + w_{,z}^0) + \sigma_x^0 w_{,x} + \tau_{xz}^0(1 + w_{,z})]_{,x} + [\tau_{xz} w_{,x}^0 + \sigma_z(1 + w_{,z}^0) + \tau_{xz}^0 w_{,x} + \sigma_z^0(1 + w_{,z})]_{,z} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the superscript ()⁰ is removed for the convenience of notation. The membrane primary prebuckling state of orthotropic plates whose material axes are parallel to the geometric axes can be truly simulated by

$$\sigma_x^0 = -p, \quad \sigma_z^0 = \tau_{xz}^0 = 0 \quad (5)$$

For any kind of orthotropic layer, the exact constitutive equations can be stated as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{xz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C'_{11} & C'_{13} & 0 \\ C'_{13} & C'_{33} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C'_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_z \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

in which, the reduced stiffness coefficients C'_{ij} , ($i, j=1, 3$) can be derived from the general three-dimensional constitutive equations in terms of C_{ij} . The displacements for prebuckling state are derived as follows.

$$u_{,x}^0 = -\frac{C'_{33}}{C'_{11}C'_{22} - C'^2_{12}} p, \quad w_{,z}^0 = \frac{C'_{12}}{C'_{11}C'_{22} - C'^2_{12}} p, \quad u_{,z}^0 = w_{,x}^0 = 0 \quad (7)$$

The simplified buckling equations are stated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} [\sigma_x(1 + u_{,x}^0) - pu_{,x}]_{,x} + [\tau_{xz}(1 + u_{,x}^0)]_{,z} &= 0 \\ [\tau_{xz}(1 + w_{,z}^0) - pw_{,x}]_{,x} + [\sigma_z(1 + w_{,z}^0)]_{,z} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and the simply-supported boundary conditions for the buckling state are simulated by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x(0, z) = \sigma_x(L, z) &= 0 \\ w(0, z) = w(L, z) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where L is the length of the plate. Using Eqs.(5-7), the buckling equation, Eq.(8), can be expressed in terms of displacements as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \frac{C'_{33}}{C'_{11}C'_{22} - C'^2_{12}} p)[C'_{11}u_{,xx} + C'_{55}u_{,zz} + (C'_{12} + C'_{55})w_{,xz}] - pu_{,xx} &= 0 \\ (1 + \frac{C'_{12}}{C'_{11}C'_{22} - C'^2_{12}} p)[(C'_{12} + C'_{55})u_{,xz} + C'_{55}w_{,xx} + C'_{33}w_{,zz}] - pw_{,xx} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

For the simply-supported plate, the solution to the boundary value problem described in Eqs.(9) and (10) can be obtained by assuming the following solution form

$$w = f(z) \sin qx \quad (11)$$

where $f(z)$ is the unknown function of z and the quantity q is defined as $q = q(n) = \frac{n\pi}{L}$, L is the longitudinal length of the plate and n is number of wave in longitudinal direction. By eliminating the inplane displacement variable, u , in Eq.(10), we find that the functions $f(z)$ are defined by the solution to the following ordinary differential equation.

$$f^{(4)} - 2aq^2 f'' + bq^4 f = 0 \quad (12)$$

where

$$a = \frac{I}{2C_{22}^i C_{55}^i} (C_{11}^i C_{22}^i - C_{12}^{i2} - 2C_{12}^i + C_{55}^i - \frac{C_{22}^i P}{1 - \frac{C_{33}^i}{C_{11}^i C_{22}^i - C_{12}^{i2}} P} - \frac{C_{55}^i P}{1 + \frac{C_{12}^i}{C_{11}^i C_{22}^i - C_{12}^{i2}} P}) \quad (13)$$

$$b = \frac{I}{C_{22}^i C_{55}^i} (C_{11}^i - \frac{P}{1 - \frac{C_{33}^i}{C_{11}^i C_{22}^i - C_{12}^{i2}} P}) (C_{55}^i - \frac{P}{1 + \frac{C_{12}^i}{C_{11}^i C_{22}^i - C_{12}^{i2}} P})$$

The function $f(z)$ is expressed as follows.

$$f(z) = \sum_{j=1}^4 A_j \exp(m_j z) \quad (14)$$

where, A_j are constants, provided that the m_j are all distinct. The various values m_j are given by

$$\begin{matrix} m_1 = \pm q \sqrt{a + \sqrt{a^2 - b}}, & m_3 = \pm q \sqrt{a - \sqrt{a^2 - b}} \\ m_2 = \pm q \sqrt{a + \sqrt{a^2 - b}}, & m_4 = \pm q \sqrt{a - \sqrt{a^2 - b}} \end{matrix} \quad (15)$$

The composite material properties considered here are such that $a^2 - b > 0$ in Eq.(15). Consequently the m_j are all real and distinct and the coefficients A_j are all real. The displacement and stress components now take the following form. The remaining boundary conditions at the top and the bottom surfaces of the plate, for the buckling problem, are as follows.

$$\sigma_z(x, 0) = \sigma_z(x, h) = 0, \quad \tau_{xz}(x, 0) = \tau_{xz}(x, h) = 0 \quad (16)$$

where h is the thickness of the plate.

Applying the boundary conditions (Eq.(16)) lead to a system of a nonlinear eigenvalue problem with four simultaneous equations for eigenvalues p and eigenvectors A_j .

SOLUTION FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES

For the laminated composite plate (Fig.1), denoting h_i to be the thickness of the i^{th} layer ($i=1, 2, \dots, m$, where m is the number of layers) the total plate thickness $h = \sum_{i=1}^m h_i$. An assumption of the uniform prebuckling stress in each layer, which is equivalent to the membrane assumption used in plate theories, is made for the composite plates. That is,

$$\sigma_x^{0(i)} = -p, \quad \sigma_z^{0(i)} = \tau_{xz}^{0(i)} = 0 \quad (17)$$

in which the superscript (i) is an index used to identify quantities in the i^{th} layer. The displacements for prebuckling state expressed in Eq.(7) are valid in each layer. Therefore the solution procedure for the derived boundary value problem which is described in Eqs.(9-16) is also valid within each layer. To establish continuity of traction and displacement at the interfaces between layers we must satisfy the following conditions in local coordinates.

$$\begin{matrix} \tau_{xz}^{(i)}(x, h_i) = \tau_{xz}^{(i+1)}(x, 0) \\ \sigma_z^{(i)}(x, h_i) = \sigma_z^{(i+1)}(x, 0) \end{matrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(i)}(x, h_i) &= u^{(i+1)}(x, 0) \\ w^{(i)}(x, h_i) &= w^{(i+1)}(x, 0) \end{aligned} \quad i=1,2,\dots,m-1 \quad (18)$$

Using the above continuity equations and the remaining boundary conditions expressed in Eq.(16), a set of global nonlinear eigenvalue equations of size of $4m \times 4m$ are obtained for solving the critical buckling load, p , of the laminated composite plate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As an illustrative example, the critical load is determined for an orthotropic plate with various length-to-thickness (L/h) ratios. The material properties (typical for graphite/epoxy composites) are listed below, where L signifies the direction parallel to the fibers, T the transverse direction and ν_{LT} is the Poisson's ratio measuring strain in the transverse direction under uniaxial normal stress in the L direction.

$$\begin{aligned} E_L &= 25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_T &= 10^6 \text{ psi} & G_{LT} &= 0.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ G_{TT} &= 0.2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{LT} &= \nu_{TT} = 0.25 \end{aligned}$$

In this example, L corresponds to x -direction and T corresponds to y -direction as shown in Fig.1. Figures 2(a) and 2(b) present the critical load from the exact elasticity solution, which are normalized with respect to the value obtained using the classical laminate theory (CLT), and are compared with those obtained using the classical laminate theory, the first-order^[11] and the refined third-order theory^[1, 11, 12], for a wide range of L/h ratios. Although the four solutions merge for sufficiently thin plates, CLT exhibits a significant deviation from the other theories as shown in Figs.2(a) and 2(b). For $L/h=5$, the critical buckling load predicted by the exact elasticity solution is only about 25% of the value predicted by CLT. However, the results of the refined third-order theory show perfect agreement with those obtained using the exact elasticity solution over a large range of the length-to-thickness ratios, including very thick plates. Since the refined third-order theory does not account for the transverse normal effect, this much indicates that the transverse normal effect is less important in the buckling problem of simply-supported orthotropic plates.

(a) Thin and moderately thick plates (b) Thick plates
Fig.2 Comparison of critical load for orthotropic plates

Next, results are obtained for $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ graphite/epoxy composite laminates and are compared with those obtained using the two-dimensional theories described above. The results of the normalized critical load are presented in Fig.3(a) for a range of length-to-thickness ratios varying from thin to moderately thick. In an extreme case where the plate is thin enough, all results converge to the same solution. As seen from Fig.3(a), at lower values of L/h , deviations are observed from CLT. However, once again, the refined third-order theory show good agreement with the exact elasticity solution for thin and moderately thick laminates. However, for thick laminates ($L/h < 10$), even the refined third-order theory exhibits significant deviation from the

exact elasticity solution (Fig.3(b)). For example, at $L/h = 5$, the critical load predicted by the first-order theory is 39% higher while the critical load predicted by the refined third-order theory is 11% higher than the value obtained using the exact elasticity solution. This phenomenon is very different from what is observed for orthotropic plates and is largely due to the complexity of transverse shear and normal stress distributions in composite laminates.

Fig.3 Comparison of critical load for $[0^0/90^0/0^0]$ plates

An angle-ply graphite/epoxy composite laminate is also examined. The stacking sequence for this example is $[-45^0/45^0]_S$. As shown in Figs.4(a) and 4(b), less deviations are observed in the critical load values, using all four solution techniques, compared to those exhibited by moderately thick and thick cross-ply laminates. However, deviations are still observed between the results of the refined third-order theory and the exact elasticity solution over a wide range of L/h values, including very thin laminates. Although these errors are small (not exceeding 2%), it still means that these two-dimensional theories have certain intrinsic deficiencies in modeling the buckling of angle-ply composite laminates.

Fig.4 Comparison of critical load for $[-45^0/45^0]_S$ plates

Of particular interest, in the present cases, are the inplane displacement u , the out plane deflection w , and the transverse stresses τ_{xz} and σ_z at the buckling state. The elasticity solutions for these functions are illustrated in Figs.5 and 6 for the orthotropic plates and in Figs.7 and 8 for the three-layered composite laminates. For the thick orthotropic plate ($L/h = 5$), it is interesting to note that the distribution of w (Fig.5(b)) not only varies along the thickness but is also asymmetric with respect to the mid-plane. The distribution of τ_{xz} (Fig.6(a)) is symmetric with

respect to the mid-plane and the distributions of u and σ_z (Figs.5(b) and 6(b)) are antisymmetric. It is expected in this case that the stress σ_z is really small due to the small value of the variation of the deflection along the thickness (less than 2% of the value of σ_z). Obviously, the distributions of u can be well fitted by the third-order polynomials. This is why the refined third-order theory can model the shear deformation of the thick plates successfully. For the three-layered composite laminates with moderate thickness ($L/h = 15$), a very striking departure is observed (Figs.7 and 8) from the prediction for orthotropic plates due to the difference in geometric stiffness properties of the adjacent layers in the laminated plates. The distribution of w (Fig.7(b)) is symmetric with respect to the mid-plane in this case. Since the derivatives of u and τ_{xz} are not continuous at the interfaces of layers (Figs.7(a) and 8(a)), it is incorrect to use continuous polynomials to simulate the distributions of such quantities. This is

(a) Inplane displacement (b) Out of plane deflection
 Fig.5 Displacement distribution along the thickness for orthotropic plate, $L/h = 5$

(a) Transverse normal stress (b) Transverse shear stress
 Fig.6 Stress distribution along the thickness for orthotropic plate, $L/h = 5$

(a) Inplane displacement (b) Out of plane deflection
 Fig.7 Displacement distribution along the thickness for three-layered laminates, $L/h = 15$

(a) Transverse normal stress (b) Transverse shear stress
 Fig.8 Stress distribution along the thickness for three-layered laminates, $L/h = 15$

why in this case the refined third-order theory is not as successful in predicting the buckling load as it is in the case of orthotropic plates. The value of σ_z is also small in this case as shown in Fig.7(b).

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research was supported by the U.S. Army Research Office, Grant number DAAH04-93-G-0043, Technical monitor, Dr. Gary Anderson.

REFERENCE

1. J. N. Reddy, A General Nonlinear Third-Order Theory of Plates with Moderate Thickness. *Int. J. Non-linear Mechanics*, **25**, 677-686(1990)
2. M. Cho and R. R. Parmerter, Efficient Higher Order Composite Plate Theory for General Lamination Configurations, *AIAA J.*, **31**, 1299-1306(1993)
3. K. H. Lo, R. M. Christensen and E. M. Wu, A High-order Theory of Plate Deformation (Part 2: Laminated Plates). *J.Appl.Mech.*, **44**, 669-676(1977)
4. N. J. Pagano, Exact Solutions for Composite Laminates in Cylindrical Bending. *J. Composite Materials*, **3**, 398-411(1969)
5. N. J. Pagano, Exact Solutions for Rectangular Bidirectional Composites and Sandwich Plates. *J. Composite Materials*, **4**, 20-35(1970)
6. N. J. Pagano and S. J. Hatfield, Elastic Behavior of Multilayered Bidirectional Composites. *AIAA J.*, **10**, 931-933(1972)
7. N. J. Pagano, Influence of Shear Coupling in Cylindrical Bending of Anisotropic Laminates. *J. Composite Materials*, **4**, 330-343(1970)
8. A. K. Noor and W. S. Burton, Three-Dimensional Solutions for Antisymmetrically Laminated Anisotropic Plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **57**, 182-188(1990)
9. N. J. Pagano and A. S. D. Wang, Further Study of Composite Laminates Under Cylindrical Bending. *J. Composite Materials*, **5**, 521-528(1971)
10. A. K. Noor and W. S. Burton, Assessment of Shear Deformation Theories for Multilayered Composite Plates. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, **42**, 1-13(1989)
11. J. N. Reddy, *Energy and Variational Methods in Applied Mechanics*. John Wiley & Sons. 1984
12. E. J. Barbero and J. N. Reddy, Nonlinear Analysis of Composite Laminates Using a Generalized Laminated Plate Theory. *AIAA J.*, **28**, 1987-1994(1990)
13. C. P. Wu and C. S. Hsu, A New Local High-Order Laminate Theory. *Composite Structures*, **25**, 439-448(1993)
14. J. M. T. Thompson and G. W. Hunt, *A General Theory of Elastic Stability*. John Wiley & Sons. 1973